

THE ROLE OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: *Today, interaction between different languages and cultures has become an integral part of everyday communication, and therefore, the ability to engage in dialogue with people from different cultures is an important and valuable skill. Language serves as the primary tool for establishing intercultural communication. Modern realities require that those learning a foreign language not only master theoretical aspects—phonetics, vocabulary, and grammar—but also be prepared to effectively and fully participate in intercultural interaction.*

Keywords: *intercultural communication, intercultural competence, culture shock, foreign culture, cultural dialogue, worldview.*

In today's world, interaction between different languages and cultures has become commonplace, making the ability to establish contact with representatives of other cultures particularly valuable. Language is the primary tool for intercultural dialogue. Today, foreign language learners are required not only to master its phonetics, vocabulary, and grammar, but also to be prepared to fully and effectively participate in intercultural communication.

Language and culture are closely interrelated and mutually complement each other. Language is the primary mechanism for transmitting and reinforcing cultural values, norms, and beliefs. At the same time, language itself is shaped by culture: without culture, language would lose its foundation, like water without a spring or a tree without roots. Therefore, when teaching a foreign language, it is essential to consider the cultural component: studying the traditions and customs of native speakers helps develop students' effective communication skills.

The interaction of different cultures is commonly referred to as intercultural communication. It involves the development of a number of key competencies: intercultural, communicative, and foreign-language professional. Intercultural competence presupposes the ability to

successfully interact in a multinational and multicultural environment and occupies a central place in the professional training of modern specialists.

Familiarization with another culture requires the need to build communication and interpersonal relationships with its representatives, as well as solving communication problems in the language of that culture in accordance with its norms and rules. To successfully achieve these goals, it is important to be able to manage language, actions, emotions, values, and beliefs, which is only possible through personal experience, trial and error.

Intercultural competence develops when a learner of a foreign language and culture transcends their own boundaries and becomes a mediator between different cultural systems. Intercultural competence is understood as the willingness and ability to interact with representatives of other cultures. Language and culture are inextricably linked: learning a language is impossible without becoming familiar with a culture, just as mastering a culture is linked to understanding its language. Thus, effective communication in a foreign language requires not only communicative but also intercultural competence. The synthesis of these two forms of intercultural communicative competence reflects the ability to effectively interact in intercultural settings.

According to O.D. According to Mitrofanov, intercultural competence represents "the interconnection of an individual's ability to realize oneself in a dialogue of cultures and in the process of mastering another linguistic culture while simultaneously developing a person's cultural experience". Its structure includes the following components:

- knowledge of cultural values and communication rules;
- skills that include the acquisition of new knowledge, its critical evaluation, and practical application;
- mental processes such as analysis, synthesis, and cross-cultural cognition;
- an attitude expressed in openness to new experiences, curiosity, and a willingness to embrace a different culture.

Mastering these components prepares specialists to perceive international changes in the professional sphere and creates the conditions for self-realization. It is important to note that, despite the different interpretations of the composition of intercultural communicative competence among different researchers, they all agree: developing this competence is a key goal of foreign language teaching. It ensures the

ability to freely navigate a foreign language environment and use the language appropriately in a variety of communication situations.

Intercultural communicative competence includes a number of components:

- linguistic, which involves knowledge of the language system;
- Sociolinguistic, associated with the ability to express thoughts using linguistic units and rules;
- Sociocultural, reflecting knowledge of the national and cultural behavioral characteristics and speech norms of native speakers;
- Social (pragmatic), manifested in the desire and ability to communicate with others;
- Strategic (compensatory), ensuring the ability to correct speech, fill in communication gaps, and improve other types of competencies;
- Discursive, enabling the construction and interpretation of text based on appropriate strategies;
- Subject-based, associated with the ability to navigate information content;
- Intercultural, determining readiness for successful interaction using a foreign language.

The presence of a large number of competencies requires their unification into a holistic system. In this system, intercultural competence plays a key role, as it integrates other types of competencies. As researchers note, "language, being the main expression of cultural identity, simultaneously acts as the main mediator in intercultural communication."

A student learning a foreign language must not only express their thoughts competently but also consider the cultural norms accepted in the native society. Mastering a language also means becoming familiar with a different value system and a different worldview. Therefore, an integrative approach based on a dialogue of cultures, which takes into account differences in mentality and worldview, is of particular importance in the educational process.

Communicative competence encompasses the strategies and mechanisms necessary for effective communication. Cultural competence, on the other hand, presupposes knowledge of political realities, phraseological units, dialectal expressions, and other linguistic features. According to A.P. Sadokhin, it is important to analyze real-life examples of intercultural interaction in the educational process, as this helps overcome the difficulties of communicating with representatives of

other cultures [6, p. 50]. Consequently, foreign language teaching should be aimed not only at developing linguistic skills but also at developing cultural competencies that ensure successful communication in an international environment. Participation in intercultural dialogue inevitably involves such phenomena as culture shock, adaptation, and the interpretation of various situations. Teachers should prepare students for potential difficulties—whether traveling abroad or interacting with foreigners in their own country. The process of adapting to a new culture, known as acculturation, goes through several stages:

1. The excitement phase, associated with interest in novelty;
2. The culture shock phase, when feelings of disappointment and stress arise;
3. The recovery phase, which involves gradual adaptation to the new culture;
4. The adaptation phase, which involves overcoming barriers and accepting the new culture.

These stages are natural and, to a certain extent, inevitable. At first, a person experiences excitement, eager to learn new things, visit significant places, and make new connections. However, over time, they begin to encounter incomprehensible or unfamiliar phenomena, which can cause stress and feelings of alienation. Gradually, the individual learns to perceive differences not as a threat, but as the characteristics of another culture, and successfully adapts, finding their place in the new society.

To reduce the risk of culture shock when learning a foreign language, students need to be prepared for intercultural communication by developing intercultural competence. This can be achieved through comparative analysis of native and foreign cultures, as well as practical activities including dialogues, role-playing, and case studies.

Developing intercultural awareness should be an integral part of foreign language teaching, as it contributes to the development of intercultural communicative competence, which is one of the key goals of language education. Language is inextricably linked to culture: it is shaped by it and simultaneously expresses it. Therefore, learning a language also presupposes the study of culture.

Effective foreign language acquisition is only possible through the development of intercultural communicative competence, as knowledge of vocabulary and grammar alone does not ensure successful interaction with representatives of other cultures. Mastering the cultural component

becomes a prerequisite, and teaching culture is a crucial tool in this process.

Intercultural communicative competence allows students to understand the social norms and practices of another culture, reduces the risk of misunderstanding, and makes communication more effective. For this reason, its development should be considered one of the primary goals of foreign language teaching.

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